

OPTIMAL DESIGN OF METAL AND COMPOSITE THIN-WALLED STRUCTURES WITH FLUTTER CONSTRAINT

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ABSTRACT

This paper deals with the optimal design of metal and composite thin-walled structures with flutter constraint and gauge requirements. By using Sequential Quadratic Dual Programming (SQDP) method, the optimal solution of each subproblem is presented analytically, which has greatly increased the optimization efficiency. The introduction of the relaxation factor has successfully eliminated the phenomenon of constraint violation caused by the poor linearity of flutter speed with respect to reciprocal design variables. Subsonic doublet-lattice method combined with V-g method is used to calculate the flutter point. Natural vibration modes are obtained by the spectral transformation Lanczos method. Two test problems are solved with our program at the end of the paper.

INTRODUCTION

With more and more application of composite materials on aircraft lifting surfaces, the problem of aeroelastic tailoring has attracted more and more attention. Through aeorelastic tailoring, that is, by changing the orientation and thickness of the laminate ply, the aircraft aerodynamic performance can be improved greatly. During the last decade, many scholars have obtained many valuable results (a good survey is given by Ref. (1)). But so far, the application of such programs to real aircraft structures is still very rare. Besides the complicatedness of this problem, a great deal of computer time is another reason. People have to choose between the decrease of algorithm generality and the more simplification of the structure model. The SQDP method² used in this paper can quickly perform the iterative design process. For single constraint problems, it can give out the optimum of each subproblem in analytical form. Because the relationship between flutter speed and design variables is very complicated, some problem arises in using this method. When the design point violates the constraint, it usually cannot come back to the feasible region. To solve this problem, a relaxation factor is introduced which will prevent the design point into the unfeasible region too far. Also this factor plays an important role in the convergence of our method.

Doublet-lattice method³ is used to calculate the unsteady aerodynamics, and flutter point is generated by automatic interpolation, which makes the flutter analysis fast and accurate. The spectral transformation Lanczos method⁴ is used to get free vibration modes.

At the end of this paper, a metal and a composite wing box are optimized with our program (RSQDP) under flutter speed constraint.

OPTIMIZATION SCHEME

The problem is:
 $\min W(A)$

s.t. $F(u) \leq 0$

$$\underline{A}_i \leq A_i \leq \bar{A}_i, \quad i=1,2,\dots, m$$

where $W(A)$ is the structural weight, A is the m -vector of design variables; $F(u)$ is the flutter constraint; $\underline{A}_i, \bar{A}_i$ are lower and upper bounds of the i th design variable.

For an arbitrary design variable vector $A=(A_1, A_2, \dots, A_m)$, considering variable link, we divide it into n groups. In each group, the variable values are the same. Let n_i denote the variable number in the i th group, we have the structural weight:

$$W = \sum_{i=1}^m \rho_i L_i A_i = \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i / y_i \quad (1)$$

where $y_i = 1/A_i$ is reciprocal design variable, $\alpha_i = \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} L_{ij} \rho_{ij}$ and ρ_{ij} is the density of the j th element in the i th group. For plate element, A_i is the thickness of the plate (metal) or the number of plies in some direction (composite); L_{ij} is the area of the plate element (metal) or the plate area multiplied by lamina thickness (composite); For bar element, A_i is the cross-sectional area (metal) or the number of plies in some direction (composite); L_{ij} is the bar length (metal) or bar length multiplied by lamina thickness and mean end width (composite). Here we only consider the case in which the orientation of the laminate ply is fixed and the design variable is ply thickness only.

Expanding formula (1) to the quadratic term at the present design point A_0 , we have:

$$\bar{W} = W_0 + b^T X + X^T C X \quad (2)$$

where

$$b^T = \left(-\frac{\alpha_1}{y_{01}^2}, -\frac{\alpha_2}{y_{02}^2}, \dots, -\frac{\alpha_n}{y_{0n}^2} \right) \quad (3a)$$

$$C = \text{diag} \left(\frac{\alpha_1}{y_{01}^3}, \frac{\alpha_2}{y_{02}^3}, \dots, \frac{\alpha_n}{y_{0n}^3} \right) \quad (3b)$$

$$X = (\delta y_1, \delta y_2, \dots, \delta y_n) \quad (3c)$$

Now, we deal with constraint condition. For flutter constraint, we have:

$$F(u) = u^* - u \leq 0 \quad (4)$$

where u is the flutter speed, u^* is the corresponding lower limit. Expanding $F(u)$ linearly at the current flutter speed u_0 , we have:

$$F(u) = B^T X - M \quad (5)$$

where

$$B^T = \left(\frac{1}{y_{01}} \frac{\partial u}{\partial A_1}, \frac{1}{y_{02}} \frac{\partial u}{\partial A_2}, \dots, \frac{1}{y_{0n}} \frac{\partial u}{\partial A_n} \right) \quad (6a)$$

$$M = u_0 - u^* \quad (6b)$$

For gauge constraint, we simply treat them in the following way: if one variable exceeds its lower or upper bounds in an iteration, it'll have the value of that bound.

Thus we change the primal problem into the following subproblem A:

$$A: \min \bar{w}, \text{ s.t. } B^T X - M \leq 0$$

The Lagrangian function of this problem is:

$$L(X, \lambda) = w_0 + b^T X + X^T C X + \lambda (B^T X - M) \quad (7)$$

From the K-T condition, at the optimum, we have :

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial X} = b + 2CX + \lambda B = 0 \quad (8a)$$

$$B^T X - M \leq 0 \quad (8b)$$

$$\lambda \geq 0 \quad (8c)$$

from (8a) we have:

$$X = -C^{-1} (b + \lambda B) / 2 \quad (9)$$

substituting (9) into (7) yields:

$$L(X, \lambda) = \bar{L}(\lambda) \quad (10)$$

where

$$\bar{L}(\lambda) = \bar{w}_0 + M_1 \lambda + M_2 \lambda^2 \quad (11a)$$

$$\bar{w}_0 = b^T C^{-1} b / 4 - w_0 \quad (11b)$$

$$M_1 = b^T C^{-1} B / 2 + M \quad (11c)$$

$$M_2 = B^T C^{-1} B / 4 \quad (11d)$$

According to the dual theory, we know that subproblem A can be transformed into the following problem B:

$$B: \min \bar{L}(\lambda), \text{ s.t. } \lambda \geq 0$$

This is a single constraint problem which can be solved analytically. From $\bar{L}'(\lambda) = 0$, we have $\lambda = -M_1 / 2M_2$. If $M_1 / 2M_2 \geq 0$, then $\lambda^* = 0$; If $M_1 / 2M_2 < 0$, then $\lambda^* = -M_1 / 2M_2$, where λ^* is the solution to problem B.

Substituting λ^* into (9), we can get X, then

$$Y_1 = Y_0 + X \quad (12)$$

$$A_1 = 1 / Y_1 \quad (13)$$

where the subscript 1 represents the modified design. Based on this new design point, another iteration can be made.

However, in actual calculation, it has been found that when the design point violates the constraint, it usually cannot get back to the feasible region in the above method. This may have something to do with the accuracy of the sensitivity analysis (the effect of the vibration shape change on aerodynamics is not taken into consideration), the highly non-linearity of constraint is another important reason. To solve this problem, a "relaxation factor" has been introduced, that is, when $(\partial u) / (\partial A_i) > 0$, we replace λ^* with $(\lambda^*)^{\epsilon_k}$, where ϵ_k is the "relaxation factor", which is used to amplify the effect of λ^* in the following formula:

$$x_i = -(\lambda^*)^{\epsilon_k} \frac{\partial u}{\partial A_i} - \alpha_i) y_{oi} / 2 \alpha_i \quad (14)$$

With the introduction of ϵ_k , the optimization process is stabilized and the convergence is improved.

From (12) and (14), because $y_{1i} > 0$, we have:

$$1. \geq \epsilon_k > \lg \theta_i / \lg \lambda^* \quad \text{if } \lambda^* < 1 \quad (15)$$

$$1 \leq \epsilon_k < \lg \theta_i / \lg \lambda^* \quad \text{if } \lambda^* > 1 \quad (16)$$

where

$$\theta_i = 3 \alpha_i / \frac{\partial u}{\partial A_i} \quad (17)$$

If the design point lies far from the unfeasible region, then $\lambda^*=0$, we will have:

$$y_{li} = 3y_{oi} / 2, \quad A_{li} = 2A_{oi} / 3 \quad (18)$$

If all the elements take part in the design, the weight will be reduced by 2/3. Because the element size is reduced proportional to each other, the vibration modes of the structure are the same as those in the last iteration.

SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS

Sensitivity analysis is performed according to Ref.(5). The vibration mode change on aerodynamics is not taken into consideration.

The derivative of generalized aerodynamics with respect to reduced frequency is obtained from finite difference method. For details see Ref.(5).

TEST EXAMPLES

1. Test problem I: Metal Rectangular Wing

A rectangular wing from Ref.(6) is optimized with our program. Aerodynamic model and FEM model are shown in Fig.1 and Fig.2 respectively. $E=7.38 \times 10^9 \text{ kg/m}^2$, $G=2.84 \times 10^9 \text{ kg/m}^2$, $\nu=0.3$, structural density $\rho_s=2768.04 \text{ kg/m}^3$, air density $\rho_a=1.068 \text{ kg/m}^3$. The lumped mass at the tip is 11.34 kg each.

In the FEM model, we treat the panels at the both sides and the webs as shear panel elements, so twelve imaginary bars of small area must be posted at the both sides. And they don't take part in the design. The upper and lower skins are idealized with membrane quadrilateral elements. From the practical point of view, we let the corresponding variables on the upper and lower surfaces be the same and divide the model into 3 segments. In each one, the related variables are the same. The numbers of variables are shown in Fig.2. The initial values are the same as Ref.6. For minimum gauge constraints, bar is $6.45 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^2$, plate $2.54 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}$. The original analysis results are shown in Table 1.

The iteration results are shown in Table 2 (the lumped masses are not included in the weight W_i).

Table 1 Initial flutter results

	$u(\text{m/s})$	$\omega(\text{Hz})$	$\bar{u}^*(\text{m/s})$
RSQDP	238.4	9.4	238.4
Ref.6	242.9	8.8	242.9

Table 2 Iteration history

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
W_i (kg)	87.42	63.07	47.42	37.38	31.08	26.93	24.19
u_i (m/s)	238.4	246.2	252.3	255.0	258.4	260.7	261.9
ω_i (Hz)	9.4	9.4	9.0	8.6	8.2	7.9	7.6
ϵ_i	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8

Table 2 ----continued

	8	9	10	11	12	13
W_i (kg)	22.82	22.78	20.81	19.45	19.57	19.56
u_i (m/s)	260.7	262.6	249.6	238.3	239.3	238.4
ω_i (Hz)	7.5	7.5	7.1	6.9	6.9	6.9
ϵ_i	0.8	0.9	0.98	0.98	0.98	

From Table 2, we can find that the weight drops down very fast, and it converges after 13 iterations with the help of the relaxation factor which varies with each iteration. The initial and final values of the variables are shown in Table 3. The area of each bar element reaches its lower limit.

Table 3-1 Normal stress quadrilateral elements (10^{-4} m)

No.	Initial	Ref.(6)	RSQDP	No.	Initial	Ref.(6)	RSQDP
1	10.16	9.40	7.96	4	10.16	11.07	9.94
2	10.16	8.56	7.96	5	10.16	2.54	7.52
3	10.16	10.86	9.94	6	10.16	2.86	7.52

In Table 4, the initial and final structural weights are listed. 2. A Rectangular Wing of Metal and Composite Structure Replacing the twelve metal normal stress quadrilateral plates with corresponding composite ones yields a new composite box wing model. The

Table 3-2 Shear panel elements (10^{-4} m)

No.	Initial	Ref.(6)	RSQDP	No.	Initial	Ref.(6)	RSQDP
1	20.32	18.19	11.27	9	20.32	2.98	8.15
2	20.32	31.47	11.27	10	20.32	2.54	8.15
3	20.32	2.54	11.27	11	20.32	5.26	8.15
4	20.32	2.54	11.27	12	20.32	2.54	8.15
5	20.32	2.54	9.22	13	10.16	2.54	2.54
6	20.32	27.34	9.22	14	10.16	7.87	2.54
7	20.32	15.43	9.22	15	10.16	2.89	6.92
8	20.32	2.54	9.22				

orientations of the plies are fixed to be $0^\circ, \pm 45^\circ, 90^\circ$. The properties of the composite material are: $E_1 = 2.11 \times 10^{10} \text{ kg/m}^2$, $E_2 = 1.90 \times 10^9 \text{ kg/m}^2$, $\nu_{12} = 0.21$, $G_{12} = 4.92 \times 10^8 \text{ kg/m}^2$, $\rho = 2006.8 \text{ kg/m}^3$, lamina thickness $t_0 = 1.32 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}$.

Table 4 Structural weight (kg)

	Initial weight	Final weight
Ref.(6)	87.4026	18.1141
RSQDP	87.4189	19.5594

For variable link, we let the corresponding variables in each segment and on the upper and lower surfaces be the same. And in each composite plate element, the laminae in $\pm 45^\circ$ are the same. The lower limit for each composite ply is 1 lamina. Others are the same as in test problem I. For metal and composite elements, ϵ_k differs in each iteration. The flutter speed constraint is 238.4 m/s. The iteration history is shown in Table 5.

Table 5 Iteration history of composite box wing

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
W_i (kg)	108.13	72.13	48.35	33.58	28.07	22.13	17.99
u_i (m/s)	405.2	331.2	274.7	241.7	261.8	277.3	275.4
ω_i (Hz)	11.1	9.7	8.2	7.1	6.9	6.7	6.4
ϵ_{imet}			0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8
ϵ_{icom}			0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8

Table 5 ---- continued

	8	9	10	11	12
W_i (kg)	15.87	15.24	14.39	13.85	13.85
u_i (m/s)	279.6	276.1	260.3	250.3	250.2
ω_i (Hz)	6.3	6.2	6.0	5.9	5.9
ϵ_{imet}	0.8	0.95	0.98	0.98	
ϵ_{icom}	0.8	0.85	0.9	0.9	

The final variable values are shown in Table 6. All the bars reach their minimums.

Table 6.1 Metal plate elements (10^{-4} m)

No.	Initial	Final	No.	Initial	Final	No.	Initial	Final
1,2	20.34	6.42	7.8	20.32	5.70	13	10.16	2.54
3,4	20.32	6.42	9.10	20.32	5.33	14	10.16	2.54
5,6	20.32	5.70	11,12	20.32	5.33	15	10.16	4.74

Table 6.2 Composite plate elements (number of laminae)

No.	Initial			Final		
	45°	0°	90°	45°	0°	90°
1,2	10	10	10	2	1	1
3,4	6	6	6	3	1	1
5,6	2	2	2	2	2	1

Table 7 Analysis results of the rounded optimal design

W (kg)	u (m/s)	ω (Hz)
15.21	276.8	6.1

In Table 6.2, the final number of plies is rounded off to the nearest whole number which is bigger than it. The analysis of the final rounded results is shown in Table 7. With the same flutter constraint, the composite box wing is much lighter than the metal one, which shows the advantage of using composite materials.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper applies the sequential quadratic dual programming method to flutter speed constrained optimization problem. The calculating speed for each iteration is very fast. The introduction of the relaxation factor is quite effective, which has successfully overcome the difficulty caused by the highly nonlinearity and stabilized the convergence. Because of the quickness of iteration, we can use this method to modify the original structural design at the first several iterations, then we use the more sophisticated optimization package, which has multi-constraint conditions, such as strength, stiffness and flutter, to continue the design process. In this way, a great deal of computing time can be saved.

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Fig.1 Aerodynamic model

Fig.2 FEM model